

The Influence of Social Media on Students' Perception of Social Studies Education in Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative case study investigated the influence of social media on students' perceptions of social studies education. The purpose was to explore how students perceive social media's credibility as an educational resource, its effectiveness in enhancing learning, and the impact of online engagement. Thirty (30) social studies students, fifteen (15) teachers, and five (5) parents from three tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria, participated in the study. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with students and teachers and focus group discussions with parents. The findings revealed that students acknowledge social media as a valuable tool for accessing diverse resources and engaging in discussions, supplementing traditional learning. However, concerns regarding information credibility and the potential for misinformation were also evident. Students emphasized the importance of interactive features, like comments and debates, for enhancing understanding. They also suggested improvements such as dedicated educational sections and verified content areas within social media platforms. The research is limited by its qualitative nature and specific geographical context, potentially affecting generalizability. The sample size, while appropriate for qualitative research, may also limit broader inferences. The practical implications suggest that educators should integrate social media into curricula strategically, providing guidance on critical evaluation of online information and encouraging purposeful engagement. Social media platforms could enhance their educational value by incorporating features such as verified content sections and robust moderation. The study contributes to the discourse on digital learning in social studies education, highlighting both the potential and challenges of using social media.

Keywords: Education, Higher education, Social media, Social studies, Sokoto state, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Digital technology has enabled the establishment of online platforms, creating an environment where learners from around the world can engage with educational content. These platforms are not restricted by geographical boundaries: Students from any part of the world — from America to Asia; Africa to Caribbean — can now enrol in a course offered by an Ivy League university in the United States, something that was previously unfathomable. Moreover, Aldahdoh, Nokelainen and Korhonen (2020)

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posit that Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) such as Coursera, edX, and Udemy have democratised access to high-quality education from prestigious institutions, making it more affordable and accessible. Social media, one of the by-products of digital technology, enable educators and students to connect with peers, experts and professionals from around the world (Anderson, 2020). Social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and YouTube, foster collaboration between instructors and students and expose users to a variety of perspectives.

One of the benefits of social media for learners—in general—is the ease of networking and collaboration. Platforms such as Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and Facebook allow students to connect not only with their peers but also with experts, educators and professionals across the globe, and such connections can lead to the exchange of diverse ideas and opportunities for collaborative projects across borders, especially for higher education learners (Chugh, Grose, & Macht, 2020). Most scholarly studies have agreed that social media has both negative and positive educational mileage for teachers and higher education learners and the overall sustainability of education (Chukwudi et al., 2016; Abbas et al., 2019; Aldahdouh, Nokelainen and Korhonen, 2020; Chugh, Grose, and Macht, 2020; Anderson, 2020; Al-Rahmi et al. 2022).

However, some of these studies were mainly conducted using quantitative methodologies to examine the general use or abuse of social media in the highly modernised and westernised societies. Other group of studies that focus on less technologically advanced, underdeveloped countries apply quantitative data collection method in investigating the broader impact of social networking sites on education in Pakistan (Appel, Marker and Gnams, 2019; Abbas et al., 2019), in Malaysia (Al-Rahmi et al., 2021; Al-Rahmi et al., 2022) and in Uzbekistan (Solidjonou, 2021). Consequently, a smaller group of studies examined social media use in higher education within the northern Nigerian context. Chukwudi et al. (2016), for instance, focused their scientific investigation in Nigeria's South Western state of Ogun, using quantitative research methodology.

As no past studies have offered a specific and sufficient theoretical and qualitative methodological account of higher education students' perception of social media use in teaching and learning, particularly in north-western part of Nigeria, there is a paucity of literature on the subject — especially on learners' awareness of social media in social studies education. To fill this research gap, this study attempts to build a theoretical framework on the conceptual underpinnings of social media use to explore how tertiary institution students of Sokoto State perceive social media as an educational resource for learning social studies subject. In building such a theoretical framework, this study will make the following contributions. Drawing on the perspective of social constructivism theory, the study will argue that knowledge is a social construct and, as a result, one of the most effective teachings and learning method is collaborative learning. To this end, our paper addresses three questions:

- **RQ1:** Do higher education students consider social media as veritable educational tools for learning?
- **RQ2:** How often do higher education students log on Facebook to search for, or study, a social studies concept?
- **RQ3:** What challenges affect higher education students from learning social studies on social media?

Furthermore, through qualitative case study design, this study will explain the benefits of student's peer-to-peer interaction and how their collaboration will influence them to use social media tools to virtually interact with men and materials and further their social studies learning. Thus, this study is structured as follows: First, the paper discusses the literature and arguments on the relationship between social media use and social constructivist theory. Second, it describes the qualitative research methodology used in the current study. Third, the paper presented the results of the major findings of the study. Fourth, the paper discussed the findings of the study. Finally, the paper concludes with limitations and implications for future research.

Literature Review

Social media use and social constructivist theory of learning

The study will adopt the social constructivist theory of learning. Akpan et al. (2020: 49) define social constructivism as an ‘active participation’ of learners among themselves (with little support from their teachers) which is aimed at creating or constructing knowledge through ‘enquiry and discovery.’ The educational theory was introduced within the developmental work of Jean Piaget (1896-1980); it was propounded by Lev Vygotsky in 1968 and later developed by several educational and psychological scholars, such as Tony J. Watson (2001), Kenneth J. Gergen (1992) and Vivien Burr (2015), among others. According to the social constructivism theory, teaching and learning are not limited to the purview of the interaction between a teacher and a student alone. Learning is a social phenomenon, and it is more ingrained and influential when teachers allow their students to interact within their circle of peers and enquire and explore what they know and did not know among themselves (Vygotsky, 1968). The theory answers three fundamental philosophical and educational questions: What is the ontology of knowledge? What is the best mode of learning? Should macro-structures determine learner’s behaviour or should learners interact within their social circle and learn on their own?

The social construction of knowledge

The first question that social constructivism seeks to answer is on the ontological basis of knowledge. On a sound philosophical ground, Kapur (2018) noted that the theory is interested in explaining the nature of knowledge acquisition, the philosophical and empirical properties of education and the social variables that facilitate learning. Proponents of the theory contend that knowledge is socially constructed. According to Vygotsky (1968), the basic tenants of social constructivism rest on three main prisms: First, language is a social activity and an essential element in teaching and learning. Second, effective learning is enhanced by human experiences and social interactions. Third, since it takes a group of people to communicate through language and construct cognitive structures, knowledge is a socially constructed phenomenon. Social constructivists do not undermine the formal educational structure of student-teacher interaction; it does not undermine the authority of classroom lessons either.

On the contrary, proponents of social constructivism theory recognised the influence of teachers but emphasised the primacy of social learning tools, such as language, culture and human experiences as the basis upon which all learning experiences are conveyed (Vygotsky, 1968). To that extent, this research suggests that social constructivism broaden higher education teachers’ perception about the social bases of knowledge acquisition and dissemination and influences their willingness to use social media in teaching and learning. Thus, the study argues that language, culture and social experiences will have positive effect on students’ perception of social media as a veritable platform for learning.

Collaborative pedagogy as an effective learning method

The second question that social constructivists answer is what is the best method of learning? Although the theory acknowledges the notion that learning requires the use of mental faculties for it to take place, it rejects the proposition that cognition helps in teaching and learning process (Schneider et al. 2022). The central argument of the social constructivist theory is that collaboration between learners to ‘resolve specific problems or complete a task’ is the best method of learning (Al-Samarraie & Saeed, 2018). As Akpan et al. (2020: 51) noted, such learning strategies can give students the freedom to read, make mistakes and learn from their peers; it also allow them to brainstorm, share ideas, discover cause and effect relationships of constructs or create ‘something new to add to the existing stock of knowledge.’ It is this form of ‘freedom’ and flexibility that gives learners the confidence and agency to explore their curiosity in the digital world and digital media, beyond the physical walls of classroom.

Since it stresses the need for social engagements with peers in the school environment, social constructivists’ scholars suggest that teachers adopt ‘assisted discovery learning’ to enhance students’ interaction, knowledge sharing and social discovery (Omrord, 2007). Teachers’ use of ‘assisted discovery learning’ entails applying specific teaching methods, such as whole-class discussion, small group discussion method among students, or grouping students together to collaborate in completing a class assignment. This research suggests that social constructivism theory create awareness in students about

the significance of collaborative learning methods among their peers and influences them to collaborate even more with others—outside of the school environment—to enhance their learning.

Student's interaction and student's social media use

Conventional educational method of learning suggests that effective learning takes place when learners are put under an instructor and constrained in a formal classroom environment and subjected under a formal school system. Under this formal schooling system, proponents of conventional education system claim that students learn better because they are under the guidance of a professional teacher. The teacher, having undergone various teaching training—in their field of study, general training in education and class management—has the ability to not only impart knowledge in the students but also mould their behaviour in the positive direction. However, under this orthodox teaching and learning method, students are subjected to mere objects, bereft of fluidity, since teachers determine the learning experiences by having the monopoly of selecting what to teach, when to teach and how to teach. Al-Rahmi (2022, cites Henrie, Halverson and Graham, 2015), supports this view by stating that ‘traditional learning techniques in research group members may affect friendly conversations [among students].’

As social media became part of everyday social life of people, it is time for educational institutions to use social media tools to expand students' friendly conversations. Facebook — as one of the leading social media tools — is an efficient platform for increasing learners' engagement online; it enables active learning with a greater eagerness to gain information; it has higher quality knowledge sharing opportunities with other students and generate a sense of belonging (Chawinga, 2017). However, Chawinga's findings fail to account for the various learning challenges students face on social media, such as the tendency to be distracted by friends and the voluminous entertainment content and the uncertainty about the quality of learning students receive on social networking sites. This study acknowledges these challenges and proposes that, although these challenges exist, students who interact together will also have a desire to do so in digital contexts.

METHODOLOGY

The current study used a qualitative research design, a research approach that focuses on exploring and understanding how individuals experience a particular phenomenon or event (Yin, 2018). This design aims to gather rich data to capture the essence of human experiences, focusing on the meaning and perception of those experiences from the participant's perspective (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Study setting

The research was conducted in Sokoto State, located in the North-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Established in 1996, Sokoto State consists of twenty-three local government areas, with Sokoto city serving as its capital. These local government areas include Binji, Bodinga, Dange-Shuni, Gada, Goronyo, Gudu, Gwadabawa, Illela, Isa, Kebbe, Kware, Rabah, Sabon-Birni, Shagari, Silame, Sokoto-North, Sokoto-South, Tambuwal, Tangaza, Tureta, Wamako, Wurno, and Yabo. Geographically, the state is situated between longitude 4°8'E and 6°54'E and latitude 12°N and 13°58'N (Ango et al., 2014). It spans a landmass of approximately 28,232.375 square kilometers. Sokoto State shares borders with the Niger Republic to the north, Zamfara State to the east, and Kebbi State to the south and west. According to the National Population Commission (NPC, 2020), the state has a population of 6,696,999, with about 74% of its inhabitants residing in rural areas, while 25.8% live in urban centers.

The cultural composition of Sokoto State is rich and diverse, with the majority of its population being Hausa and Fulani. Minority groups such as the Zabarmawa and Tuareg are also present, with Hausa serving as the common language across the region. As the historic seat of the Sokoto Caliphate, the state is predominantly Muslim and is recognized as an important hub for Islamic scholarship in Nigeria. The Sultan of Sokoto, who leads the caliphate, serves as the spiritual leader of Muslims in the country. Over recent decades, education in Sokoto State has seen notable improvements. Primary and secondary education have benefited from initiatives like the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program, which aims to enhance access, enrollment, and completion rates. Despite these efforts, the education sector continues to face challenges such as poverty and insufficient infrastructure, which impede progress.

Higher education in the state is supported by various institutions that contribute to research, learning, and workforce development. Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS), is a leading federal institution, renowned for its strong focus on Islamic studies, humanities, sciences, and health-related disciplines. The university attracts students from across Nigeria and beyond due to its diverse academic offerings. Additionally, Sokoto State University focuses on improving higher education access for local residents, while institutions such as the Shehu Shagari College of Education, Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, and the recently established Shehu Shagari University of Education address the need for teacher training and technical education. These institutions collectively contribute to the educational and socio-economic development of Sokoto State.

Sampling and data collection

Purposive sampling was used to select thirty (30) social studies students from the three selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State (Shehu Shagari College of Education, Shehu Shagari University of Education, and Sokoto State University); fifteen (15) teachers from the three selected higher institutions and five (5) parents (see Table 1). In all, fifty (50) respondents were chosen for this study. Data were collected from the respondents through the In-depth Interview Guide (IDI), administered to students and teachers (ranging from one to two hours), and through Focus Group Discussion (FGD) conducted with parents within the study setting to provide their opinions and perceptions on social media influence on higher education students’ perception of social studies. This technique provided an opportunity to explore the perceptions of the respondents and, through the application of a qualitative approach, identified factors that the respondents believed were critical for their social studies learning experiences.

The interview involved the lead researcher—and two other research assistants—residing, observing and interviewing the respondents for about two months (the total duration for the data collection meetings) between December 2024 and January 2025. As stated earlier, purposive rather than random sampling was used to select the respondents based on their ability to answer the study’s research questions. Respondents were given the opportunity to give consent by accepting or declining to participate in the interview and focus group discussion session.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Respondents’ profile

<i>Individual characteristics</i>	<i>Number of respondents</i>
<i>Final year social studies students</i>	
Male	10
Female	5
<i>Second year social studies students</i>	
Male	4
Female	3
<i>First year social studies students</i>	
Male	4
Female	4
<i>Teachers (social studies)</i>	
Male	9
Female	6
<i>Parents</i>	
Fathers	3
Mothers	2
Total	50

Source: Authors

The lead researcher, together with two research assistants (a male and a female), visited the respondents in the study settings to conduct the interviews. Before the meetings, the date, time and place of the interview were agreed upon. It is also important to note that the researchers employed a Focus Group Discussion session with five participants (parents of the students) as a method of triangulation and a means to validate the study's findings (Usman, 2016). The focus group session was conducted by the female research assistant employed by the lead researcher, and it was conducted inside the house of one of the parent's research participants. The researchers conducting the interviews are familiar with the culture and reflexes of the Hausa, being Hausa themselves. This is a strength of this research as it enabled the researchers to obtain demographic information and develop the sample frame. Although, it could be argued that this may have led to confirmation bias. However, several authors have argued that proper knowledge of the population concerning the importance of quality sample size outweighs the disadvantages due to bias (Patel et al., 2003). Of course, the size of the data set brings up potential limitations since, despite the benefits of inductive methods, limiting the interviews to 50 respondents might have some implication regarding the generalisability of the data.

Data analysis

The research involved three main stages. First, interviews were conducted in Hausa and then transcribed into English by the researchers. The interviews were conducted in Hausa because Hausa is the native language of the respondents; allowing them to speak freely in their native language would ease their conversation. Second, the transcriptions were analysed using thematic analysis to identify dominant and interesting contexts of discussion (Guest et al., 2012). Third, the interviews were coded using the qualitative data analysis software NVivo, which helped to identify and explore concepts and categories. In the first step of data analysis, the data are coded into general themes by assigning a word or phrase to each category.

In the second step, axial coding, data are put back together in new ways by making connections between themes. Open coding enables researchers to familiarise themselves with each case as a stand-alone entity and allows unique patterns to emerge before attempting to identify cross-case patterns (García and Welter, 2011, p. 388). In the third step, selective coding, a core category is selected with the goal of interpreting them. This process started with a pre-set list of codes derived from prior knowledge of the subject and concepts identified during the review of the literature. Dominant quotes are used to punctuate the discussion and identify individual respondents.

FINDINGS

The study revealed three major themes: Social media's credibility, social media as a learning tool, engagement with people and content and recommendations for improvement. Figure 1 summarises our analysis by showing how we progressed from primary to codes to theme identification.

Credibility and trust

During the interview session with the participants, they generally acknowledged the credibility of social media information but emphasized the need for caution in trusting content without verification. Many respondents valued expert-driven content on platforms like LinkedIn and Twitter, where professionals often engage and share insights. However, there was a shared concern about misinformation, as one respondent noted:

Sometimes I'm skeptical about the content on social media because not everything is verified, and misinformation spreads easily. That said, there are reliable sources and pages run by credible organizations or individuals. For instance, I've found academic articles and discussions shared by educators and experts that are really insightful. It's just important to double-check the information and cross-reference with other sources to avoid relying on false data.

This highlights the dual nature of social media as both a valuable resource and a platform requiring careful scrutiny. Participants agreed that while social media is not a substitute for traditional academic sources, it serves as a useful supplementary tool for research and learning when credible sources are identified.

Source: Computed from interview data

Social media as a learning tool

Participants recognized social media as an effective tool for enhancing academic learning, particularly in the realm of social studies. The ease of accessing diverse resources and real-world applications of theoretical concepts was a major benefit. One participant explained thus:

Social media has been surprisingly effective for social studies learning. I've joined groups where people share resources, case studies, and real-world applications of theories and concepts, which are easier to grasp. Discussions in the comments often spark deeper insights, and concepts are easier to grasp through interactive content like videos and infographics.

This reflects the interactive and engaging nature of social media, which allows for a more dynamic and accessible learning experience. Social media was seen not only as a space for sharing educational materials but also as an environment for real-time engagement and feedback. Many participants also pointed out that platforms like Facebook provided a sense of community where students could interact with peers and experts, enhancing the overall learning process.

Engagement with people on social media

The interactive nature of social media was frequently highlighted as a key element in enhancing learning experiences. Participants emphasized the value of engaging with others through comments, discussions, and debates, which provided a richer understanding of social studies topics. As one respondent put it:

The interactive aspect of social media is one of its biggest advantages for learning. The comments section often adds depth to posts, with people sharing diverse perspectives and examples. Sometimes, debates emerge, and those are especially insightful. It's like having a global classroom where everyone brings something unique to the table.

The opportunity to engage in these dialogues, often with people from different parts of the world, enabled participants to view social studies topics from various angles. Social media also allowed learners to build networks with peers and experts, creating spaces for continuous learning and collaboration. The combination of these features significantly enriched participants' academic experiences and learning outcomes.

Recommendations for improvement

While social media platforms were viewed positively in terms of their educational potential, participants offered several recommendations to improve their effectiveness in supporting higher education students. Many suggested the introduction of more structured learning features, such as dedicated educational sections or verified content areas, to ensure that students access high-quality, trustworthy resources. As one respondent noted:

Absolutely! Social media platforms could add features like dedicated learning hubs or verified content sections for students. They could also improve access to academic articles or partner with educational institutions to share exclusive resources. Enhanced moderation to reduce misinformation would be great too. It's already a helpful tool, but these changes could make it even better for education.

This quote captures the desire for platforms to evolve into more robust educational tools that provide not only information but also curated, reliable academic content. Participants agreed that better moderation of content and partnerships with academic institutions could improve the overall educational value of social media. These improvements would ensure that students are guided towards useful, credible resources while reducing the impact of misleading or unreliable content.

DISCUSSION

This study explored the role of social media in enhancing social studies learning among higher education students, with a focus on the credibility of information, the effectiveness of social media as a learning tool, the impact of engagement and interaction, and suggestions for improvement. The findings reveal both the strengths and challenges of using social media in academic contexts, providing insights into how these platforms can be leveraged for educational purposes while also highlighting the limitations and risks associated with them. The results are discussed in relation to existing literature and theory, particularly social constructionism in education, which emphasizes the role of social interaction and community in the construction of knowledge.

A central theme in the findings was the credibility of information shared on social media. Participants expressed a general awareness of the potential for misinformation on these platforms but also identified credible sources, particularly content shared by experts or reputable organizations. This finding resonates with existing literature, which underscores the difficulty in assessing the credibility of social media content. For instance, Veletsianos and Kimmons (2016) note that social media's unregulated nature allows both reliable and unreliable information to coexist, creating a challenge for users to discern what is credible. In this study, participants indicated a critical approach to information consumption, suggesting that while social media can be a valuable resource, it is essential to verify content before relying on it.

The fact that students recognized the necessity of cross-checking information aligns with the social construction theory of education, which argues that knowledge is collaboratively constructed through

interaction within a community. This finding implies that social media can be an important tool for knowledge creation when used judiciously, with active participation from informed individuals. The implication for educators and students is that social media can complement traditional academic sources, but users must cultivate media literacy skills to navigate these platforms effectively.

However, there are notable limitations. The unfiltered nature of social media means that misinformation can spread rapidly, often without appropriate checks or accountability. As such, while social media offers an opportunity for democratized knowledge sharing, it also presents challenges in ensuring that the content is accurate, particularly for academic purposes. This highlights the need for educational interventions that help students develop critical skills in assessing the credibility of online sources.

The study found that social media was perceived as a valuable tool for enhancing academic learning, especially in social studies. Participants reported using social media not only for accessing resources but also for engaging with academic content and discussions. This aligns with the growing body of research that highlights the potential of social media to facilitate collaborative learning and expand access to diverse educational resources (Junco et al., 2011). The findings also suggest that social media platforms serve as a repository for real-world applications of social studies concepts, which is often a gap in traditional academic settings. For instance, students noted that discussions on social media helped contextualize theoretical concepts in real-world scenarios, thus deepening their understanding. This aligns with the social construction theory, which emphasizes the importance of active engagement in the learning process. The theory suggests that knowledge is constructed through social interactions, and social media offers a platform for students to engage in these interactions across geographical and cultural boundaries.

By participating in online discussions, sharing resources, and interacting with peers and experts, students engage in collaborative knowledge building that extends beyond the classroom. In this sense, social media serves as an extension of the classroom environment, fostering a dynamic and inclusive approach to learning. The implication of these findings is significant for higher education. Social media can be integrated into formal educational practices as a supplementary tool for enhancing learning. Institutions could develop strategies to encourage students to use social media to engage in discussions, share educational resources, and participate in global conversations about social studies. However, one limitation of this finding is the potential for distraction. The vast and diverse content available on social media can sometimes divert students' attention away from academic learning. This underlines the importance of guiding students in using these platforms for educational purposes, ensuring that their engagement is purposeful and focused.

The interactive features of social media were another prominent theme in the findings. Participants highlighted how the ability to engage in discussions, debates, and commentaries on posts enriched their understanding of social studies topics. This finding supports the idea that social media, when used appropriately, can promote active learning, as it fosters peer-to-peer interaction and knowledge sharing. Vygotsky's (1978) social constructionist theory suggests that learning is a social process that occurs through collaboration and dialogue. The interactive nature of social media enables students to engage in this collaborative process on a global scale, broadening their perspectives and enhancing their critical thinking. The findings from this study align with literature that emphasizes the role of social media in providing opportunities for cross-cultural interactions and diverse viewpoints (Manca & Ranieri, 2016). One participant's comment that social media functions like a "global classroom" encapsulates the value of these platforms in enabling students to engage with individuals from various cultural, academic, and professional backgrounds. These interactions not only enrich students' understanding of social studies concepts but also expose them to multiple viewpoints, which is essential in fostering critical thinking and global citizenship.

While the engagement and interaction on social media can enhance learning, there are potential drawbacks. Not all interactions are constructive, and debates can sometimes become polarized or unproductive. In some cases, discussions may devolve into arguments rather than collaborative knowledge construction. This highlights the need for moderators and educational guidelines to ensure that

interactions remain respectful and focused on learning. Thus, while engagement and interaction are valuable, the quality of these interactions must be managed to ensure their educational benefit.

The final theme that emerged from the findings was the participants' suggestions for improving social media as an educational tool. Many participants proposed the introduction of more structured and verified content on social media platforms to enhance their educational value. This included the creation of dedicated educational sections, better access to academic resources, and more robust systems for verifying the accuracy of information. These suggestions are consistent with calls in the literature for social media platforms to assume more responsibility in curating content and ensuring that educational resources meet academic standards (Manca & Ranieri, 2016). The social construction theory implies that the quality of the learning environment plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of knowledge construction.

Structured, well-moderated environments are more conducive to collaborative learning, as they provide a clear framework for engagement and knowledge sharing. This suggests that social media platforms could enhance their educational value by creating spaces specifically designed for academic use, where content is curated, verified, and organized for educational purposes. The implication of this finding is that educational institutions and social media companies could collaborate to build more educationally focused platforms that support learning and knowledge sharing. The limitation of this suggestion, however, is the decentralized nature of social media. Platforms like Facebook and Twitter are vast, user-driven spaces, which makes it challenging to enforce consistent educational guidelines or ensure the accuracy of content across all posts. As such, while improvements are possible, there are significant logistical and organizational challenges that may hinder the widespread implementation of these recommendations.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the role of social media as an educational tool for enhancing collaborative learning in social studies. The findings reveal that social media platforms, particularly Facebook, serve as valuable resources for accessing diverse perspectives, engaging in interactive discussions, and supplementing traditional learning methods. However, while students recognize the potential of these platforms in facilitating academic engagement, concerns about credibility and misinformation persist. The study also highlights the importance of digital literacy in enabling students to critically assess online content and utilize social media effectively for academic purposes. The findings align with the Social Constructionist Theory in Education, emphasizing how knowledge is co-constructed through interaction, discussion, and shared experiences in digital spaces. The study underscores the necessity for improved moderation and fact-checking mechanisms on social media platforms to enhance the credibility of academic content.

Additionally, educational institutions should integrate social media literacy training into curricula to equip students with the skills to navigate online learning environments critically. While this study provides valuable insights, certain limitations must be acknowledged. The findings are based on qualitative data, which may not be generalizable across different educational contexts. Future research should explore the role of other social media platforms and investigate the long-term impact of social media-based learning on academic performance. Despite these limitations, this study contributes to the growing discourse on digital learning and offers practical recommendations for improving the use of social media as an academic tool. By addressing credibility concerns and fostering structured engagement, social media can become a powerful and reliable platform for higher education learning in the digital age.

Implications for Research, Policy and Practice

Implications for research

The findings of this study highlight the need for further research into the evolving role of social media in higher education, particularly in social studies. Future studies should explore how different social media platforms, beyond Facebook, contribute to academic engagement and critical thinking. Additionally, longitudinal studies could assess the long-term impact of social media-based learning on students' academic performance and knowledge retention. Comparative research across different educational

contexts and disciplines would also help determine whether the benefits and challenges identified in this study are universally applicable or context-specific. Lastly, investigating the role of artificial intelligence (AI) and content moderation in improving the credibility of educational materials on social media remains an important area for future exploration.

Implications for policy

The study underscores the necessity of integrating digital literacy and media verification training into higher education policies. Educational institutions and policymakers should develop frameworks that promote responsible social media use for academic purposes, ensuring that students, beyond Sokoto, can critically evaluate online information. Universities should also collaborate with social media companies to enhance fact-checking mechanisms, ensuring that misleading or false educational content is minimized. Policies should encourage the creation of dedicated academic spaces within social media platforms, where credible, peer-reviewed content is prioritized. Governments and educational regulatory bodies must also consider ethical guidelines that address issues such as data privacy, misinformation, and the responsible use of social media in academic settings.

Implications for practice

For educators, the findings suggest the need for structured integration of social media as a learning tool. Lecturers and instructors should leverage interactive platforms for discussions, assignments, and collaborative projects, while also guiding students on how to assess the credibility of online information. Universities should provide training sessions and workshops on digital literacy, helping students develop critical thinking skills when engaging with social media content. Furthermore, educators should encourage students to follow reputable academic groups, participate in constructive discussions, and use social media as a supplementary tool rather than a primary source of academic information. Lastly, social media platforms should consider developing specialized features that support formal learning, such as verified educational subspaces and expert-moderated discussion forums, to enhance their utility in higher education.

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